

ARCTIC
PASSION

Arctic PASSION recommendations towards a
**Sustained Arctic
Observing System**

GERMAN
ARCTIC OFFICE

1. Introduction and Background

The scientific, societal, economic, and environmental challenges associated with the changing Arctic are immense and require a coordinated approach towards observing and data collection. The EU funded project [Arctic PASSION](#) (“Pan-Arctic observing system of systems: Implementing observations for societal needs) aims to overcome the still existing challenges, such as fragmentation and lack of tailoring of observations to user needs, by co-creating a more integrated pan Arctic observing system in international collaboration, including Indigenous Peoples and local communities. It shall allow access to unrestricted, high quality, science-based Earth observation information as well as consented Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge. It shall be better tuned to the needs of society, allow monitoring environmental changes, reduce uncertainty in predictions, and support decision-making. The main objectives of Arctic PASSION include to enhance and integrate Arctic observations, improve Arctic data management, optimise observing networks through numerical modelling, deliver own new services for users, and assess societal and economic benefits of the new observing system.

With a consortium consisting of 43 partners, we put together our diverse expertise on what is needed for a better coordinated and integrated, more useful and more equitable Arctic Observing System and seeking ways to sustain it. End of 2024 a survey was performed within the consortium to find out what are the aspects needed for a long-term establishment of an Arctic Observing System. 22 responses were received as free-text responses across all Work Packages of the Arctic PASSION consortium. These responses are summarised in the below formulated recommendations. The fundamental prerequisite is sustained funding and we are therefore addressing these recommendations to the Arctic Science Funders Forum.

2. Recommendations

Arctic PASSION recommendations towards a better coordinated Arctic Observing System, with improved observations and a structured Arctic Data system are classified in three categories:

1. Coordination and Governance
2. Observations
3. Data

CATEGORY 1: TOWARDS A BETTER COORDINATED ARCTIC OBSERVING SYSTEM

RECOMMENDATION 1.1.

Need for sustainable coordination of an Arctic Observing System

(including observing networks, Indigenous Peoples, local communities, research institutions, organisations, different levels of governance such as municipal administrations, stakeholders, end-users, managers of systems/equipment/logistics/infrastructures, international field campaigns, ...)

Why? The plethora of actors involved in Arctic observations needs a platform for cooperation and coordination. With a multilateral dialogue among the actors, observations and services can be better targeted towards societal needs and benefits of communities. It improves the exchange of existing observations as well as the Arctic data structure and sharing. Through a coordination platform, end-users and target audiences can be better involved in the co-design and prioritisation of variables, platforms and delivery interfaces.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

Find a mechanism to sustainably fund long-term observations in the Arctic, and their coordination:

- Support SAON (Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks) and its Secretariat in a substantial and long-term capacity to continue their mission to facilitate, coordinate and advocate for coordinated international pan-Arctic observations.
- Long-term commit to the [European Polar Coordination Office](#), a newly established coordinating body connecting European projects, initiatives, the science community and the European Commission. This coordination office on the European level and a North American equivalent will also be an important body in the structuring of a coordinated Arctic Observing System. Similarly, sustained funding for thematically focused coordination efforts is of high relevance, also, such as for the Arctic Ocean Regional Alliance - ArORA.
- Support the inclusion of relevant intercultural, cross-sectoral and transdisciplinary actors in funding calls to contribute to enhancing international institutional cooperation, e.g., between research institutions and municipal administrations and/or communities across the Arctic. Ensure that a breadth of multifaceted perspectives and individuals are included in decision-making towards an Arctic observing network, e.g., in terms of disciplines, knowledge systems, governance levels, communities, sectors, end-users, genders, ages, socio-economic strata, ethnicities, etc.

RECOMMENDATION 1.2.

Support [SAON's ROADS process and the SAV Expert Panels](#) and members, in particular support for Indigenous contributions (co-leads, members, speakers, etc.) is needed

Why? SAON's Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS) aims to improve Arctic observing and data systems through better and new partnerships. The Shared Arctic Variables (SAV) concept defines sets of observables that can help to solve problems on a local or regional scale in the Arctic. SAVs are responsive to the information needs of everyone affected by the rapid changes taking place in the Arctic. The idea is to draw on the capacity of all the communities to co-design and co-manage observing efforts by gathering representatives from each into thematic Expert Panels, and to include Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge as well as science into the process. Results from the Expert Panels will contribute to SAON's ROADS process. The two projects, Arctic PASSION (EU & Canada) and [RNA CoObs](#) (Research Networking Activities for Sustained Coordinated Observations of Arctic Change, USA), (co-)funded the establishment of SAV Expert Panels to pilot a set of SAV themes. When the projects end, SAON will need support to continue.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

- Invest in SAON's ROADS process and the development of Shared Arctic Variables by supporting SAON financially.

RECOMMENDATION 1.3.

Enhance the sharing of logistical platforms through a network of research stations and research infrastructures

Why? A network of infrastructures is needed to stay connected, share sampling protocols, and harmonise data collection across the Arctic. Arctic PASSION has shown how important and challenging it is to harmonise data collections that date back a long time, to fill gaps, and to make them comparable between stations. Especially stations that are setting up new weather stations and ecological monitoring benefit greatly from being connected with a network of stations that have a long history of monitoring such parameters. Networking activities and sharing best practices will also help identify gaps in monitoring. This network includes Automatic Weather Stations (AWS), a key infrastructure that provides instantaneous measurements and long-term trends.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

- Find mechanisms for long-term funding of the [INTERACT Non-Profit Association](#), a network of 74 research stations and infrastructures (plus an additional 21 Russian stations currently on pause), such as core funding and a host office. The network works on improving data collection and accessibility, knowledge exchange on measured parameters and shared challenges, as well as research access. INTERACT is also represented in SAON (see 1.1.).
- Provide continued funding for maintaining existing infrastructures such as scientific Automatic Weather Stations (currently removed, unmaintained or inoperable after project's end) (low cost-effort).

RECOMMENDATION 1.4.

Equal inclusion of Indigenous Peoples, and other Arctic (or local) communities and their organisations as well as other (marginalised) groups and the equity of different knowledge systems

Why? Indigenous Peoples, and other Arctic (or local) communities are closely connected to the Arctic environment and have unique and valuable knowledge. Together with academic knowledge, changes in the Arctic can be interpreted holistically and the quality and relevance of data can be improved. There are high barriers and bureaucracy to involve them as partners, little time to build collaborations before writing a proposal and therefore difficulties to co-create projects without funding salaries, etc.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

Change the funding and decision-making structure to a more equitable and inclusive Arctic observing system:

- Funding streams for dedicated inclusive and holistic approaches in Arctic research.
- Allow Indigenous Peoples, and other Arctic (or local) communities or their representing organisations to lead their own projects, be beneficiary partners and co-leads in research projects.
- Flexible funding for the pre-proposal phase to establish relationships/partnerships and to involve community members without an administrative overhead (compensation for time).
- Funding to hire trusted local facilitators who can build trust, share knowledge, and encourage the use of the service. Workshops and training sessions are also essential to ensure that communities understand and benefit from the system while contributing their own observations.
- Allocate resources for programmes that enable Indigenous Peoples, and other Arctic (or local) communities to participate actively in data collection, monitoring, and interpretation processes. This may include training, employment opportunities, and long-term partnerships to support local experts and community-based observing networks.

CATEGORY 2: TOWARDS IMPROVED OBSERVING SYSTEMS

RECOMMENDATION 2.1.

Long-term funding for long-term monitoring is key: Long-term observations are the foundation on which detection, understanding and prediction of climate change and its effects are based.

Why? The impact of ongoing climate change and increased human activity in the Arctic can only be understood based on long in-situ time-series. Long-term measurements are important to have a baseline to compare with and to understand rates of change and are also needed in regions, where currently no major environmental or climate-related changes are happening. Many long-term records are obtained by short term projects, leading to inconsistent and intermittent time-series, and missing standardisation. For sustained and more appropriate long-term observations, we must move away from this ad hoc approach.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

- Establish a mechanism to sustainably fund long-term observing and monitoring systems/programmes in the Arctic. Evaluate options for separate funding streams for research projects and for long-term monitoring tasks. Existing infrastructure must be maintained after the implementation phase. Focus should lay on long-term monitoring of essential key variables (e.g., climate variables) and new Shared Arctic Variables.
- Allocate funding (10-year horizon) for equipment/logistics/infrastructure and running costs of in-situ observation systems with a sufficient geographical coverage. Representative in-situ observations are inherently valuable, but are also needed for calibration and validation of remote observation systems and models.
- Put the mechanisms and multinational resources in place to allow researchers, Indigenous Peoples, and other Arctic (or local) communities as well as other actors from different nations to develop bottom-up projects to address key Arctic concerns. Similar to how the EU performs their science, but on a truly international scale. Multinational funding allows for optimal use of expertise and infrastructure as well as facilitation of data/results integration.

RECOMMENDATION 2.2.

Monitoring and observations must be based on societal needs

Why? Understanding the Arctic's complex socio-economic-environmental dynamics requires closing gaps in interdisciplinary research that addresses both environmental and socio-economic data needs. Research that combines environmental science, economics, and social science allows a better assessment of the impacts of environmental change on Arctic communities, economies, and ecosystems, as well as the inclusion of Indigenous Peoples, and other Arctic (or local) communities, users, stakeholders and relevant audiences.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

- Fund interdisciplinary research to address socioeconomic and environmental interdependencies.
- Request funding applicants to create a framework for assessing the socio-economic benefits of data articulating their value and potential impacts to society.
- Collaborate more in the development of research targeting the influence of local climate mitigation and climate adaptation policies on societal behaviour and methodologies for integrating societal behaviour concepts into climate governance at different governance levels. Observing systems and the related interdisciplinary research should lead to a sufficient level of knowledge/understanding to capture local climate change and related environmental issues.

- Require that funding calls ensure that observing systems be rooted in and flow into useful services which provide the current state and future outlook for information relevant to users outside of research: business, public sector and the general public. These services should be able to demonstrate that they reach such audiences.
- Support a pilot phase project to achieve consensus in communities on monitoring approaches and monitoring needs.
- Funding is needed to identify and fill the gaps in monitoring. Networking activities can help identify gaps.
- Include gender- and sex-disaggregated data in Arctic observations by supporting additional research time to gather statistics on the gender of data generators and users as well as information on inequalities or discrimination. Invest in training research teams about this component.

RECOMMENDATION 2.3.

Model-based support for designing an observation network and investment in a better use of new technologies

Why? When setting up new or improving existing observations, modelling can help to calculate and to make scenarios about which methods (frequency, spatial/temporal resolution, etc.) are most effective to cover the object of observation. Also, technologies themselves can be better used to overcome limitations.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

- Include a modelling approach when designing new observation networks or optimising existing ones.
- Be open to different observation modalities to maximise the potential of new technologies, which are usually developed for reasons and areas other than environmental monitoring.

RECOMMENDATION 2.4.

Need to funding research on critical gaps in cryosphere science

Why? Arctic PASSION monitors key cryosphere components such as sea ice, snow, permafrost, lake and river ice, glaciers and ice sheets because they are highly important to societally relevant issues such as food security, infrastructure, safe navigation and transportation, and way of life.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

Fund specific activities to fill cryosphere knowledge gaps:

- Invest in machine learning-related methods to monitor Arctic land ice.
- Invest in new satellite missions, especially satellite altimetry to monitor glacier mass changes.
- Invest in field observations for Arctic freshwater fluxes and subglacial discharge to understand ice-ocean interactions.

**CATEGORY 3:
TOWARDS AN IMPROVED ARCTIC DATA STRUCTURE AND BETTER KNOWLEDGE
SHARING**

**RECOMMENDATION 3.1.
Improved data handling and provision**

Why? Arctic data and metadata are still often handled and published in a fragmented manner which makes it difficult for various users to access and use the data. Producing standardised and FAIR data and metadata improves the interoperability, accessibility, use and re-use. Together with an open access, it builds the basis for knowledge, education and decision-making. The more comprehensive and detailed metadata available to describe the data record, the easier it is to find and use the actual data.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

- Require data generators to create and treat data and metadata records in accordance with state-of-the-art data management standards throughout the process of data generation to publication. Acknowledge the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles for research data management and ensure practical implementation that makes published data machine-readable. Funded scientific projects and activities should include research data management at the level of an independent work package as the standard procedure.
- Continue to require open access publication of research data in funding calls. Reserve sufficient funding for project partners for publishing articles and data with open access.
- Provide funding for timely production and dissemination of real and near real-time data and value-added products that are useful for services to society.
- Provide funding for local and remote infrastructures and citizen science to support standardised collection and transfer of data and metadata to trusted long-term data repositories, ensuring the use and reuse by the scientific community, local stakeholders, decision-makers and the global public. Specific funding can be allocated in research projects or through a network mentioned under 1.3.
- Ensure the acceptance and establishment of the CARE (Collective benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) principles when data and observations originate from Indigenous Peoples' communities or activities.

**RECOMMENDATION 3.2.
Improved data integration, use and sharing**

Why? Long-term data repositories archiving and publishing research data according to the FAIR Data Principles require continuous funding to support their services in curating and publishing submitted data, ensuring interoperability, keeping up with growing standard requirements, and training researchers and institutions, leading to significant benefits for science and society at global, community and individual levels.

Also, on other levels such as the Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P), it is important to continuously fund experienced personnel and technical infrastructure in order to bring many individual datasets together in a standardised and harmonised format, and to maintain as well as distribute global data products.

WE RECOMMEND FUNDERS TO:

- Provide permanent support for long-term data repositories and data publishers fostering FAIR research data management and facilitating access to machine-readable data at national and international level. Require trusted observation data repositories being harvested by the [SAON Data Portal](#) to aggregate datasets from different data repositories, make the data more accessible through rich metadata at discovery and use levels combined with data access services following FAIR principles. This allows re-use by, e.g., decision-makers.

- Invest in a more user-friendly interface and structure of the SAON Data Portal to better be able to find existing data for key variables and specific regions/local areas and to be able to pick up on previous measurement campaigns through accessible data and metadata. A dedicated usage case study would help to customise and improve the portal interface for users outside of research.
- Invest in a maintained data infrastructure for [Essential Climate Variables](#) (ECV) monitoring by funding central offices to bring the data and metadata together. For example: funds for the Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P) office and GTN-P database are needed.
- Invest more in digital transfer and repository solutions for knowledge developed at different levels of governance to enhance multi-level knowledge transfer and further use.